

Studies in Salt Activation. Part II. Influence of Salts on the Stability of Amylase.

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In a previous communication (Giri and Shrikhande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 273) the influence of salts on enzymic hydrolysis of starch has been examined in detail. The conditions under which salts accelerate hydrolysis have been determined. A few points regarding the mechanism of salt activation have also been discussed. It appeared possible that the accelerating effect of salts might be due to the protection of the enzyme against destruction, thereby indirectly accelerating the activity of the enzyme. No quantitative work seems to have been published regarding the stability of amylase in relation to the presence of salts. Hizume (*Biochem. Z.*, 1924, 146, 52), however, has shown that salivary amylase was protected from heat inactivation by the presence of sodium chloride and other chlorides, by sodium bromide but not by nitrate or iodide. Malt diastase, on the other-hand, was deleteriously affected by the presence of sodium chloride or sodium bromide during heating. In the experiments of Hizume, the p_H of the medium was neither controlled nor observed. Further the influence of salts on the stability of the enzyme was not investigated at varying salt concentrations. The present investigation has shown that the protective action of salts on the enzyme depends on these two factors, *viz.*, the p_H of the medium and the concentration of the salt. By suitably varying these two factors, protection, destruction or no effect on the enzyme can be found. These facts together with the qualitative nature of his results, particularly with malt diastase, indicate that further systematic investigation is necessary. It is interesting in this connection to refer to the work of Sherman and Walker (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1960) who have shown that the activating action of amino-acids on pancreatic amylase is due in part to a protection of the enzyme from deterioration in the aqueous dispersion in which it acts. The present investigation was undertaken

with a view to know whether neutral salts protect the enzyme from inactivation, and whether there is any relation between the protective action and the accelerating effect of the salts on the enzyme.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The amylase used in the present investigation was prepared from sweet potato and purified by adsorption on alumina gel and elution with phosphate buffer and final dialysis, in the manner described by Giri (*Biochem. Z.*, 1934, 275, 106). All the salts employed in the present investigation were of the highest grade of purity, either Merck's or Kahlbaum's guaranteed analytical reagents.

The method of measuring the activity of the enzyme was the same as that described in a previous communication (Giri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 338). The reaction mixture (100 c.c.) contained 1 g. of starch, and Walpole's acetate buffer of p_H 6.0, present in a total concentration of 0.04N-acetate.

The method of studying the stability of the enzyme was as follows: A series of mixtures containing acetic acid-acetate buffer of known p_H , present in a total concentration of 0.05N-acetate, and salt of known concentration were prepared in a series of resistance glass test tubes, the total volume of the mixture amounting to 5 c.c. The tubes containing the mixtures were immersed in a thermostat at 50°. After the temperature of equilibrium was established, 5 c.c. of the enzyme solution were poured into each tube and allowed to remain at the same temperature for 30 minutes. At the end of this period, 5 c.c. of the enzyme mixture were removed from each tube and the activity determined.

The activity is always expressed in terms of the velocity constant K . The activity of the enzyme which was kept at room temperature (control) was taken as the standard.

Influence of Salts on the Stability of Amylase at Varying Hydrogen-ion Concentrations.

Enzyme mixtures containing buffer of varying hydrogen-ion concentrations, with and without added salt (NaCl), were prepared. The concentration of NaCl present in the mixture was 0.05N. The mixture was kept at 50° for 30 minutes, and the activities determined. The results are given in Table I and graphically represented in Fig. 1.

In the tables V denotes relative reaction velocity and K , the activity.

TABLE I.

p_H .	Without added salt.		With 0.05N-NaCl.	
	$K \times 10^4$.	Relative reaction velocity.	$K \times 10^4$.	Relative reaction velocity.
	33.9 (control)	100	33.9 (control)	100
4.0	4.9	14.5	12.0	35.4
4.5	23.7	70.0	28.1	82.9
5.0	30.2	89.0	33.9	100
5.5	33.9	100	33.9	100
6.0	33.9	100	33.9	100
6.5	29.6	87.3	29.6	87.3

It can be seen from Table I that the activity of the enzyme is not changed by keeping it at 50° at p_H 6.0, which is the optimum p_H for the activity of the enzyme. With a view to finding out whether the salt exerts any protective influence on the enzyme at the optimum p_H , the experiment was repeated at 65° and no such effect was observed. Thus the results indicate that the salt protects the enzyme

Fig. 1.

Effect of p_H on the stability of amylase.

I—With 0.05N-NaCl.
II—Without added salt.

Fig. 2.

Influence of anion on the stability of amylase

Curves I-IV refer to NaF, NaCl, Na₂SO₄ and NaNO₃ respectively.

against destruction at the more acid region of optimum p_H . No such protective effect was observed on the alkaline side of the optimum p_H at the salt concentration investigated. On comparing the curves in Fig. 1 with those obtained in the previous communication (Giri and Shrikhande, *loc. cit.*) which indicate the influence of hydrogen-ion concentration on the accelerating effect of salt, a close similarity on the nature of the curves can be seen. Thus the salt protects the enzyme against destruction at hydrogen-ion concentrations at which it also accelerates the activity of the enzyme.

Influence of the Anion of the Added Salt on the Stability of Amylase.

With a view to ascertain whether the anion of the salt has any influence on the stability of the enzyme similar to that which it has on its activity, experiments were carried out with the fluoride, chloride, sulphate and nitrate of sodium. The composition of the mixture was the same as before, except that the concentration of the salts were varied and the p_H adjusted to 4.0. The results are presented in Table II and in Fig. 2.

TABLE II.

$p_H = 4.0$. Temperature = 50° .

Salt conc.	NaF		NaCl		Na ₂ SO ₄		NaNO ₃	
	$K \times 10^4$.	V.	$K \times 10^4$.	V.	$K \times 10^4$.	V.	$K \times 10^4$.	V.
Control	37.3	100	37.3	100	37.3	100	37.3	100
0	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2
0.01 N	12	32.2	7.3	19.5	5.9	15.8	5.8	15.6
0.02	14.9	40.0	10.8	28.9	8.9	23.8	7.3	19.5
0.05	17.3	46.4	14.1	37.8	12.3	32.9	10.9	28.9
0.10	18.8	50.4	14.1	37.8	13.3	35.6	9.7	26.0
0.20	20.9	56.0	5.3	14.2	5.0	13.4	2.0	5.4

It may be mentioned here that in view of the fact that the fluoride notably displaces the p_H of the buffered enzyme mixtures, the p_H was controlled and checked colorimetrically on an aliquot part of the solution. In this way the possibility of the enzyme solutions being diversely influenced by the difference in p_H was excluded.

The foregoing results show that the stability of the enzyme increases with the salt concentration upto a certain limit and then decreases considerably; sodium fluoride at all concentrations exerts considerable protective influence on the enzyme. Unlike the other salts the protective effect of sodium fluoride does not decrease by further increase in the concentration of the salt. This is consistent with the generally anomalous behaviour of fluorides in relation to other halides. The effectiveness of the salts in protecting the enzyme against destruction can be arranged in the following order: $\text{NaF} > \text{NaCl} > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{NaNO}_3$. It will be of interest to note here that in a previous communication on the subject, the accelerating effect of these salts on the activity of the enzyme was found to follow the same order.

Influence of the Cation of the Added Salt on the Stability of Amylase.

The hydrogen-ion concentration was maintained constant as before, and the concentrations of the salts were varied. Table III shows the nature of the results obtained.

TABLE III.

Salt conc.	LiCl		KCl		NaCl		CaCl ₂	
	$K \times 10^4$.	V.						
Control	37.3	100	37.3	100	37.3	100	37.3	100
0	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2
0.01N	4.9	13.2	4.9	13.2	7.3	19.5	16.2	43.4
0.02	7.6	20.4	8.1	21.7	10.8	28.9	15.9	42.6
0.05	13.3	35.6	13.3	35.6	14.1	37.8	13.7	36.7
0.10	11.5	30.8	12.0	32.1	14.1	37.8	7.3	19.6

The foregoing results would suggest that the protective influence of the salts investigated depends also on the nature of the cation of the salt. Thus CaCl_2 at low concentrations protectst he enzyme against destruction, while the other salts require high concentrations to protect it to the same degree. Now considering the possibility that salts accelerate the activity of the enzyme by protecting it against destruction, a similar difference in the cation influence on the

acceleration of the activity of the enzyme is to be expected from these results. But in the previous communication it was found that all the cations had the same accelerating effect on the activity of the enzyme. This discrepancy is easily explained by repeating the experiment at varying concentrations of each salt. The following are the results obtained with varying concentrations of each salt on the activity of the enzyme.

TABLE IV.

Influence of cation on the activity ($K \times 10^4$) of amylase at pH 4.0 and at 30°.

Salt conc.	LiCl.	KCl.	NaCl.	CaCl ₂ .
0	15.9	15.9	15.9	15.9
0.01N	16.6	16.4	17.5	18.0
0.02	17.5	17.5	18.1	22.4
0.05	19.6	19.6	19.8	27.8
0.10	21.4	22.0	23.4	24.5

It can be seen from the results that at low concentrations of the salt the divalent cation Ca has a more accelerating influence on the activity of the enzyme than the monovalent cations. Thus the foregoing results show that there is a parallelism between the influence of the cations on the stability and on the activity of the enzyme.

Influence of Salts on the Stability of Amylase at the Optimum and at the Alkaline side of the Optimum pH.

The experiments were repeated at pH 6.0 (optimum pH) and temperature 65°, and at pH 6.5 and temperature 50°. It was found (Table V) that the salt (NaCl) exerts no influence on the stability of the enzyme, but at high salt concentration (0.1N) it renders the enzyme less stable. This is in conformity with a similar behaviour of the salt on the activity of the enzyme. Thus it was shown in a previous communication that sodium chloride does not accelerate the activity of the enzyme at the optimum, and on the alkaline side of the optimum pH; on the contrary, the salt inhibits the activity when its concentration is high.

TABLE V.

Influence of NaCl on the stability of amylase at pH 6.0 and 6.5.

NaCl conc. (N)	..	0	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.10	
$K \times 10^4$	{ At pH 6.0	...	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	1.9
	{ At pH 6.5	...	32.6	32.6	32.6	31.7	27.4

DISCUSSION.

The object of the present investigation was to show whether the salts protect the amylase against destruction and whether there is a parallelism between the influence of these salts on the stability and on the activity of the enzyme. The results show that the conditions favourable for acceleration of the enzyme action are also favourable for the protection of the enzyme against destruction in presence of salts. Thus the salts protect the amylase from destruction at more acid region of the optimum p_H . At the optimum and at the alkaline side of the optimum p_H , they have no influence on the stability of the enzyme; on the contrary they hasten the destruction of the enzyme at high salt concentrations. Under exactly similar conditions, the salts were found to accelerate the activity of the enzyme. Secondly, the order of action of the anions and cations of the salts investigated is similar both for the protection of the enzyme and for the acceleration of the activity of the enzyme. It seems, therefore, reasonable to associate the effects of salts upon the hydrolysis of starch by the enzyme with their influence upon its stability, and to conclude that salts accelerate the activity of the enzyme because they protect it against destruction, and that stronger solutions are inhibitory because they hasten the destruction of the enzyme. It is, however, by no means contended that the protective influence of the salts on the enzyme accounts for the phenomenon of salt action.

SUMMARY.

1. The influence of salts on the stability of amylase from sweet potato has been investigated under varied conditions.
2. The salts protect the enzyme against destruction at more acid region of optimum p_H . Individual anions differ very widely in their quantitative influence on the stability of the enzyme. The salts

investigated can be arranged according to the decreasing magnitude of their effect in protecting the enzyme against destruction as follows: $\text{NaF} > \text{NaCl} > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{NaNO}_3$. The divalent cation Ca is more efficient than the monovalent cations Li and Na in protecting the enzyme against destruction.

3. An explanation has been advanced for the salt acceleration of the enzymic hydrolysis of starch. The favourable effects of salts at certain concentrations on the hydrolysis of starch by amylase appears to be associated with the increased protection of the enzyme and the inhibitive action at high salt concentrations with decreased stability of the enzyme under these conditions.

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The Heats of Transition of Triglycerides.

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The property of exhibiting a double melting point has long been regarded as a characteristic of nearly all triglycerides. Several observers* have recorded that these triglycerides melt at a certain temperature, solidify at one slightly higher, and melt again on further heating.

It will be instructive to compare the "melting points" recorded by Efremov (*Ann. Inst. Polyt. Ural*, 1927, **6**, 155), Löskit (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, **134**, 137) and Joglekar and Watson (*loc. cit.*). It should be noted that these investigators claim to have purified their specimens with enormous care, Löskit recording 60 crystallisations, while Joglekar proceeded through as many as 40.

* Guth, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1902, **18**, 169; *cf. Z. Biol.*, 1902, **34**, 78; Grün and Schacht, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 1770; *cf. Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 3692; Bömer *Z. Nat. Genussm.*, 1907, **14**, 97; 1909, **16**, 362; Bömer and Limprich, *ibid.*, 1913, **18**, 373; Kremann and Schoulz-Graz, *Monatsh.*, 1912, **33**, 1063; Smits and Bokhorst, *Proc. Acad. Wetensch.*, 1913, **18**, 681; Bokhorst, *Dissertation*, Amsterdam, 1916; Nicolet, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, **12**, 741; Grün, *Ber.*, 1921, **54B**, 2909; Klimont, *Oest. Chem. Ztg.*, 1922, **25**, 22; Joglekar and Watson, *Chem. und Med.*, 1928, **47**, 365.